

BLUEMISSION AA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission
implementation in the *Atlantic and Arctic Basin*

Best practice in methods of citizen engagement and knowledge transfer: Citizen Assemblies, workshops, and surveys

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Contents

Document Information	2
Document history and changes	2
List of Figures.....	5
1. Executive Summary	6
2. Introduction	7
3. Citizen Assemblies – CYPABL	13
4. Workshops – BlueMissionBANOS	22
5. Attitude surveys – EastSide Greenways.....	28
6. Citizen science surveys – COSEA	33
7. Conclusion and Recommendations	37
8. Bibliography.....	42
9. Appendix A.....	44

List of Figures

Figure 1: Citizen participation spectrum (PREP4BLUE Toolbox) - adapted from IAP2's Public Participation Spectrum.	10
Figure 2: Participants of the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss.	13
Figure 3: Distribution of participants in the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss, including age, gender, ethnicity, residence and disability (source: Final Report on the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss (pg. 14))	14
Figure 4: Schematic representing logic of local and regional workshops (BlueMissionBANOS).....	23
Figure 5: Klimafolkemødet banner	24
Figure 6: Local workshop in Denmark (BlueMissionBANOS).....	24
Figure 7: Local workshop in Belgium (BlueMissionBANOS).....	25
Figure 8: Advertisement of BlueMissionBANOS workshop on Klimafolkemødet website	25
Figure 9: Brainstorming post-it notes from local workshop in Belgium (BlueMissionBANOS).....	26
Figure 10: Example of an outdoor survey data collection method (EastSide Greenways).....	29
Figure 11: 'Greenway on the Go' graphic with key quotes from survey respondents (EastSide Greenway).....	30
Figure 12: 'Add Spot' screen on COSEA app (screenshot by Catriona Reid)	34
Figure 13: 'Add Spot' screen where users are prompted to add a picture of their observation and describe how it makes them feel (left), and draw an outline on an observed habitat (right) (screenshot by Catriona Reid)	35

1. Executive Summary

Marine research and governance, marked by the ever-increasing urgency of the climate crisis, is increasingly looking to citizens and stakeholders for input into co-designing and co-creating solutions to improve ocean health. In Mission Ocean, citizen engagement is a cornerstone of the Mission Implementation Plan, highlighting that a whole-of-society approach is needed to address this challenge. Involving citizens in knowledge exchange and in policy-making decisions can have many benefits. Policy processes benefit from a more holistic and direct understanding of the reality of the challenges faced by citizens in adapting to environmental change. Policy processes that include citizen engagement enhance the legitimacy of outcomes, but require trust building, transparency, and honest communication about how engagement inputs will be integrated.

Given the importance of broad engagement in policy processes, research into best practices in methods of citizen engagement, and an understanding of the fundamental concepts in deliberative and participatory democracy, is crucial.

In this report, four examples of citizen engagement methods are examined:

1. **Citizen Assemblies** (Ireland's Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss)
2. **Workshops** (BlueMissionBANOS's local workshops and regional Mission Arenas)
3. **Attitudinal surveys** (EastSide Partnership)
4. **Citizen science surveys** (SPOTTERON COSEA mobile app)

Key recommendations:

- Align local/small-scale initiatives with national initiatives when possible
- Build-in flexibility to planning and designing for citizen engagement
- Follow-up with citizens on the impact of their engagement
- Plan for reflective evaluation and impact evaluation of your initiative

Beginning with an overview of some of the seminal literature in deliberative and participatory democracy, highlighting the importance of citizen engagement to the implementation of Mission Ocean, this deliverable then examines four case studies in detail. The case studies focus on the methods, challenges, opportunities, and best practices for citizen engagement and knowledge transfer. Each case study includes detailed recommendations for each of the four citizen engagement methods, and an overview of recommendations and best practices is given in the conclusion of this document.

2. Introduction

Background: citizens, terminology, and Mission Ocean

What is citizen and stakeholder engagement and why is it important?

Solutions to marine protection and restoration, marked by an ever-increasing complexity of the causes and the consequences of climate change, require diverse viewpoints and perspectives to be considered so that the best possible solutions can be identified by scientists and policymakers. In an effort to avoid unintended consequences of restoration solutions¹, policymakers are increasingly involving stakeholders and citizens in consultation processes with a view to harnessing existing local knowledge, consulting on potential solutions, and co-producing solutions in the case of the most ambitious projects. The logic of involving citizens and stakeholders in policy decision-making and knowledge co-production processes is that input from diverse groups can help in identifying and creating a more accurate understanding of the impacts of marine restoration, meaning that solutions can be better tailored to the problem, with potential roadblocks already having been identified in the engagement phase (Huttunen et. al., 2022).

Citizen and stakeholder engagement can have many co-benefits. Policymaking and research processes benefit from an increased legitimacy of their outputs and outcomes by involving citizens and/or stakeholders (providing that this is done in a meaningful way) (Mielke et. al. 2016; Kiss et. al., 2022). Such processes also benefit by achieving a more accurate representation of the lived reality of people impacted by policy changes (particularly concerning place-based development consultation: Cortés-Cediel et. al., 2019; Kiss et. al., 2022). Citizens and stakeholders can also benefit from such processes: increased agency and feelings of empowerment for one (Elstub et. al., 2022), with the best-case scenario resulting in long-lasting relationships and networks between citizens and stakeholders which can foster long-term transformative change.

Clarification of terminology

While the terms 'stakeholder' and 'citizen' are often used interchangeably, it is important to note the key differences between these groups to set the tone for the rest of this document.

The term '**stakeholder**' most commonly refers to a group or an individual who has a **vested interest** in the outcome of the decision-making process in question, who typically also has **privileged access** to decision-makers through professional connections, news networks, or by being a legally obligated consultee². This can

¹ Bjørkan et al. (2023), 'Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of Approaches'. Milestone 6. PREP4BLUE. Available at: <https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/> [Accessed 12/12/2024]

² *ibid.*

include groups from governmental and non-governmental organisations, civil society, unions, the media, academia, and so on. Individuals can also be stakeholders regardless of gender, sexual orientation, age, or race.

However, the term '**citizen**', in the context of citizen engagement, is **more broad** than this. 'Citizen' refers to **any individual** most often living in the village, town, city, jurisdiction, or country in which the decision-making process is taking place. Notwithstanding the legalistic definition of 'citizen', meaning an individual who holds citizenship of a given nation state, in the realm of citizen engagement, 'citizen' does not necessarily hold this definition. 'Citizen' in this context simply refers to an individual who, by professional or contextual means, **does not already have privileged access to knowledge production**. In this sense, **citizens can be stakeholders, and stakeholders can be citizens**. For the purposes of this report, 'citizens' will be taken to mean any individual who does not have privileged access to consultation processes or knowledge production.

The terms '**participation**' and '**engagement**' are also used interchangeably, however a number of key differences exist. Borrowing from theories of participatory democracy (Arnstein, 1969; Escobar, 2017), '**participation**' is a **deeper form of engagement** with democratic processes with the aim of improving those processes for the future. This involves the creation of long-standing and mutually beneficial relationships between citizens and decision-makers. In ocean restoration research projects, citizen participation is often achieved through citizen science projects and initiatives.

Conversely, '**engagement**' refers to a **shorter-term, but by no means less valuable, form of citizen involvement**. Citizen engagement most often involves consultation and knowledge transfer, where citizens are involved in processes such as envisioning sustainable futures, gauging public perceptions, or developing participatory methods (Huttunen et. al., 2022). In research projects, citizen engagement often takes the form of workshops, surveys, focus groups, or World Cafés (for more methods, see BlueMissionAA Deliverable 5.6).

This report will focus on **citizen engagement**, meaning processes and methods which have engaged with citizens, being individuals lacking privileged access to knowledge production and policymakers, on a short-term or once-off basis.

Citizen engagement and knowledge transfer in the Mission Ocean context

Citizen engagement plays a fundamental role in the implementation of Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters (hereafter referred to as 'Mission Ocean'). The Mission Implementation Plan³ highlights that citizen engagement in Mission Ocean will be multi-faceted, covering a range of involvements from citizen science, co-designing collective futures for Europe with a focus on sustainable aquatic management, water stewardship, ocean literacy, arts, media and culture. This is rooted in the

³ European Commission (2021), 'Mission Implementation Plan', pg. 35. Available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_for_publication.pdf [Accessed 12/12/2024]

understanding that a “whole of society” approach is needed to ensure the success of Mission Ocean⁴. The objectives of Mission Ocean are threefold:

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
- Prevent and eliminate pollution
- Ensure a carbon neutral and circular blue economy

Given the depth and breadth of efforts required to achieve these goals by 2030 (the target end-date of Mission Ocean), buy-in from citizens is crucial (Whyte et. al., 2024). Climate change and pressures on the marine environment have often been referred to as ‘wicked problems’ (Hugel and Davies, 2020; Lonngren and van Poeck, 2020) – a term coined by Rittel and Webber (1973) – in this context referring to the complexity of both the problem of climate change and ocean health, and the solutions needed to address it. In this context, engagement with citizens can be a way to identify, predict, and address potential barriers to marine restoration solutions at an early stage. As such, citizen engagement is a key factor in ensuring the success of Mission Ocean objectives.

Knowledge transfer, at its most basic level, is about transferring knowledge and experience gained through learning or experience to another person, most often through didactic teaching (Nokes-Malach and Richey, 2015). However, within the marine science-policy interface, the term is used interchangeably with the term ‘knowledge exchange’ (Karcher et. al., 2024). In such processes, citizens and stakeholders are brought in to engage in project activities (such as workshops, roundtables, townhalls, etc.), or to participate in longer-term forms of engagement (such as participatory research or community-based research), with the goal of informing and even guiding the direction of marine science and governance projects. Such involvement of citizens is crucial for increasing the legitimacy of science-informed policy outcomes.

This deliverable will examine three methods of citizen engagement and knowledge transfer, building on the three methods identified in BlueMissionAA Deliverable D5.6, which identified Citizen Assemblies, workshops, and surveys as being three recommended methods of citizen engagement. Using four case studies, this report will extract key learnings for both **citizen engagement** and **knowledge transfer** in Mission Ocean. These learnings will be useful for future projects and for citizen engagement practitioners alike.

Methods

Literature review

A literature review was first carried out to investigate the theoretical underpinnings of citizen engagement and knowledge transfer in a Mission Ocean context, focusing on theories of participatory democracy, deliberative democracy, and knowledge co-production.

⁴ Bjørkan et al. (2023), ‘Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of Approaches’. Milestone 6. PREP4BLUE. Available at: <https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/> [Accessed 12/12/2024]

Qualitative interviews and PREP4BLUE Toolbox

The PREP4BLUE project Milestone 6 toolbox, “Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A Toolbox of Approaches⁵”, provides the foundational guiding framework for this deliverable, particularly the ‘Citizen participation spectrum’ (Figure

		DEGREE OF CITIZEN DECISION-MAKING POWER →				
		INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
CITIZEN PARTICIPATION GOAL	To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.	To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.	To work directly with citizens throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered.	To partner with citizens in each aspect of the decision, including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solutions or activities.	To place final decision-making in the hands of citizens.	
PROMISE TO THE PUBLIC	The Mission initiative will keep citizens informed.	The Mission initiative will keep citizens informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and aspirations, and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	The Mission initiative will work with citizens to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	The Mission initiative will look to citizens for advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.	The Mission initiative will implement what citizens decide and/or co-implement and co-lead initiative.	

Figure 1: Citizen participation spectrum (PREP4BLUE Toolbox) - adapted from IAP2's Public Participation Spectrum.

1) found on page 11 (subsection 2.2) of the Toolbox. This spectrum is adapted from a spectrum created by the International Association for Public Participation – the ‘Public Participation Spectrum’⁶. This spectrum compares ‘Increasing impact on the decision’ (i.e. decision-making power of citizens) with ‘Promise to the public’ and ‘Public participation goal’ to highlight five different increasing degrees of citizen participation: **Inform**, **Consult**, **Involve**, **Collaborate**, and **Empower**. This framework provides the basis for a comparative analysis of different methods of citizen engagement used in the case studies.

Data was collected through desk research and qualitative interviews. Four semi-structured interviews were conducted in total, one with representatives from each of the four case studies. The interview participants were project coordinators/managers and facilitators – in total, 7 people were interviewed (in three out of the four cases, the interviewees attended in pairs, while one individual attended alone). Interviews were conducted by UCC and SPI over the course of September-November 2024. The literature review informed the development of the interview questions, with best

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ International Association of Public Participation (2014), ‘IAP2’s Public Participation Spectrum’. Available at: https://iap2.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/IAP2_Public_Participation_Spectrum.pdf [Accessed 12/12/2024]

practice guidance in the practice of the four chosen citizen engagement case studies structuring the questions asked during the interviews. A list of questions asked is provided in Appendix A. The interviews were conducted online using Microsoft Teams which automatically generates a transcript – this transcript was then quality controlled by the lead researcher. The transcript data was then thematically analysed by the research team, identifying best practices and lessons learned from each of the case studies.

Case study selection

The case studies were selected according to the following criteria:

- **Method of engagement** (Citizen Assembly, workshop, or survey – methods identified in BlueMissionAA D5.6)
- **Broad geographic representation** (the chosen case studies are based in Ireland (Children and Young Peoples' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss); United Kingdom (Belfast EastSide Greenways); and Denmark and Belgium (BlueMissionBANOS local workshops).The COSEA citizen science app has international application, however the developer, SPOTTERON, is based in Austria.
- **Transferability of learnings** (citizen engagement processes which had completed, or which were sufficiently mature to allow for the development of learnings based on practice, were chosen to ensure that a reflective interview discussion would be possible)
- **Type of citizen or stakeholder engaged** (citizen engagement processes which engaged primarily or exclusively with *citizens*, as opposed to *stakeholders*, in line with the delineation between these terms discovered during the literature review, were prioritised).
- **Maturity** (the case studies were selected by prioritising those that were complete or sufficiently advanced to allow for reflection and identification of actionable learnings)

Scope and limitations of this report

This report presents a focused analysis of selected case studies, with an emphasis on identifying best practices and assessing the potential transferability of insights to the Mission Ocean context. It does not seek to provide a comprehensive evaluation or critique of the individual case studies. Instead, the primary objective is to extract actionable learnings that may inform future Mission Ocean initiatives.

The analysis is based on a limited sample of four case studies. While each case is examined in detail with regard to its methodological approaches and operational practices, the restricted sample size constrains the findings. As such, the recommendations derived from this report should not be interpreted as universally applicable across all citizen engagement initiatives.

The report prioritises an examination of the methodologies employed by the case studies rather than the characteristics of the citizens involved. In several instances, demographic data pertaining to participants was either unavailable or deemed non-essential to the scope of this analysis. This methodological focus reflects the intent to highlight structural and procedural elements that may be transferable, rather than to profile participant populations.

Results of the desk study (relevant documents and websites) and interviews are presented in sections 3, 4, 5, and 6, providing detailed accounts of the engagement practices, identifying best practice and lessons learned. Section 7 provides the conclusions and recommendations of this report, while section 8 provides references.

Synthesis of recommendations

Recommendations are provided on a case-by-case basis at the end of each case study and are also synthesised at the end of this report under three themes which emerged from the analysis of the interviews. These are as follows:

- Facilitation and practical considerations
- Communicating with the public
- General guiding principles and best practices

The report is structured so that a reader can either read the conclusions at the end of the report to grasp a high-level overview of key recommendations, or else a reader can pick and choose which case study interests them, and at the end of each case study, the recommendations provided are specific only to that case.

3. Citizen Assemblies – CYPABL

Background

The **Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss**⁷ was an initiative designed to empower young voices in Ireland's efforts to address the biodiversity crisis. Commissioned by the Department of Housing, Local Government, and Heritage, it aimed to educate, inspire, and gather ideas from children and young people to shape national policies and action plans, as participants' contributions are central in Ireland's strategy to protect and restore biodiversity, ensuring their voices are heard by decision-makers.

In October 2022, the Assembly brought together 35 children and young people aged 7–17 from diverse backgrounds across Ireland to share their perspectives, discuss challenges, and propose solutions to the biodiversity crisis. The initiative extends the principles of democratic engagement, traditionally reserved for adults, to younger generations, recognising the importance of involving them in environmental decision-making. Organised in partnership with Dublin City University (DCU), University College Cork (UCC), Terre des Hommes (tdh), and supported by experts in environmental governance, children's rights, and biodiversity, the Assembly provided a platform for young participants to express their needs, concerns, and priorities regarding biodiversity loss, environmental degradation, and climate change. These issues will profoundly impact their futures, making their involvement essential in crafting sustainable, forward-thinking, and equitable solutions.

The Assembly's insights contributed to the National Biodiversity Action Plan and promoted continued public dialogue, reinforcing its long-term impact among stakeholders, government actors, and the wider public. This initiative aligns with international commitments, such as Ireland's obligations under the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, linking children's rights to biodiversity protection. It also underscores the global nature of biodiversity challenges.

Figure 2: Participants of the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss.

⁷ More information about the **Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss** available at <https://cyp-biodiversity.ie/>

Engagement Process

The initiative began in early 2022 with the formation of a consortium to design and implement the assembly. Preparations started in spring, culminating in the Assembly's sessions in October 2022, held over two weekends. To familiarise participants with the process, an online session was conducted before the in-person gatherings.

The recruitment strategy aimed to ensure a geographically and demographically representative sample. Invitations were sent to randomly selected schools across Ireland. To broaden outreach, paid advertisements on social media platforms were used, leading to 510 expressions of interest. Participants were then chosen through a stratified representative sampling process⁸, based on factors such as age, sex, geography, and other demographic criteria. Unlike the standard recruitment methods for adult assemblies, which often use phone numbers or postal codes, a tailored approach was necessary for involving children.

The final group included 18 boys and 17 girls. Ethnicities were predominantly White Irish (29), with 3 Other White, and 1 each of Black/Black Irish, Asian/Asian Irish, and Other/Mixed. By residence, 13 were from cities, 12 from towns/villages, and 10 from rural areas. Geographically, participants hailed from Dublin (9), Connaught/Ulster (6), Munster (10), and the rest of Leinster (9). Age distribution spanned 7–17 years: 6 aged 7–8, 9 aged 9–10, 6 aged 11–12, 6 aged 13–14, and 7 aged 15–17. Lastly, 32 individuals reported no disability, while 3 had disabilities (Figure 3).

Additional contributions were gathered via “Open Submissions” process through the website cyp-biodiversity.ie. This allowed unselected young people to pitch in their ideas, thoughts, and solutions, through creative formats such as letters, videos, artwork, and photographs.

Figure 3: Distribution of participants in the Children and Young People’s Assembly on Biodiversity Loss, including age, gender, ethnicity, residence and disability (source: Final Report on the Children and Young People’s Assembly on Biodiversity Loss (pg. 14))

⁸ Method used in research or data collection to ensure that a sample accurately reflects the composition of a larger population. It involves dividing the population into **distinct subgroups, or strata**, based on shared characteristics (e.g., age, gender, income, education level, geographic location) and then sampling from each stratum proportionally or strategically.

The consideration of age range was crucial, as priorities and concerns vary significantly with developmental stages. From early childhood to late adolescence, children undergo rapid changes in identity, awareness, and passions. These developmental shifts produce a diverse range of perspectives within a relatively narrow age group, enriching discussions on biodiversity and environmental challenges. For example, a 7-year-old might observe a decline in insects in their backyard, offering a localised yet important insight into biodiversity loss, while a 17-year-old's broader awareness might focus on global environmental issues such as deforestation or climate change.

Both localised efforts and large-scale systemic shifts are essential for meaningful change, as they complement each other in addressing environmental challenges at all levels. Incorporating perspectives from various age groups not only clarifies issues but also facilitates the design and implementation of effective solutions.

Structure and Process

Participants were sorted into "family groups" by age, each identified by a unique mascot. Using mascots proved to be an effective strategy to both label and "gamify" the ongoing process, creating an engaging and age-appropriate framework for communication. As highlighted, these age groups are tightly condensed, and even a 2–3 year difference can significantly impact the type of language required by speakers and the level of understanding and interpretation from the listeners.

This Assembly worked in parallel to the adults Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss, which took place on the same days, highlighting the intergenerational nature of the biodiversity crisis. A representative from the adult Citizens' Assembly also participated to highlight the intergenerational aspect of the initiative.

It also aimed to serve as a model for international replication, drawing inspiration from Scotland's Climate Assembly and Children's Parliament, and involved a mutual partner, Terre des Hommes. Through this, the Assembly contributed with vital inputs to Ireland's National Biodiversity Action Plan, enhancing its inclusivity and impact.

Safeguarding and Inclusivity

Safeguarding was a priority throughout the Assembly. All adults involved underwent vetting by An Garda Síochána (the Irish Police) to ensure a secure environment for the children. Regular check-ins ensured participants' wellbeing, with facilitators adjusting schedules as needed, such as adding breaks or activities for younger children to maintain engagement. By prioritising safety, inclusivity, and accessibility, the Children and Young People's Assembly ensured a meaningful and impactful engagement process, contributing valuable insights to Ireland's biodiversity policies.

Activities and Outcomes

The Assembly process took place over **two weekends**: the first on October 8th–9th, 2022, at the Glenree Centre for Peace and Reconciliation, County Wicklow, and the second on October 22nd–23rd, 2022, at Killarney National Park, County Kerry. **The first weekend focused on education and exploration, while the second centered on developing actionable solutions.**

Weekend 1: Learning and Deliberation

The first weekend, taking place in the Glenree Centre for Peace and Reconciliation, County Wicklow, began with ice-breaker activities to foster a safe and inclusive environment. These activities helped build trust among the group and introduced the core topics of children's rights, deliberative democracy, biodiversity, and the drivers of biodiversity loss.

Session 1: What are children's rights?

Participants explored the connection between children's rights, biodiversity, and decision-making processes. Understanding children's rights was foundational to their participation. The discussion highlighted the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) and the Lundy Model⁹ of Participation, which outlines four essential steps to ensure that children's voices are heard and respected:

1. **Space** – Providing children with a safe and inclusive space to express their views.
2. **Voice** – Facilitating children's expression through accessible and meaningful methods.
3. **Audience** – Ensuring children's views are listened to by the appropriate decision-makers.
4. **Influence** – Ensuring that children's views lead to actual change, with feedback on how their input shaped the outcome.

To reinforce these concepts, activities like 'People Bingo' were used to help participants connect these concepts to participants' everyday lives, while 'Agree and Disagree' prompted discussions about the value of children's participation in decision-making processes. These activities aimed to empower participants by helping them recognise the importance of their voices in shaping broader societal issues.

The participants showcased awareness regarding the concept of "wicked problems"¹⁰ — challenges that are complex, context-dependent, and lack

⁹ Lundy, Laura. (2007). 'Voice' is not enough: Conceptualising Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. *British Educational Research Journal* - BR EDUC RES J. 33. 927-942. 10.1080/01411920701657033.

¹⁰ Rittel and Webber (1973)

straightforward solutions, often involving diverse stakeholders with conflicting values. Understanding this concept was critical for framing discussions on biodiversity loss.

Session 2: What is biodiversity loss?

In this session, participants reflected on their understanding of biodiversity and its importance, leading to a deeper sense of ownership and engagement with the topic. Their reflections included views such as:

- “A group of animals and plants working together in an ecosystem.”
- “Biodiversity is like the connection between all life. It is every living thing from wolves to a tiny blade of grass.”
- “It’s like a jigsaw. Without one piece, the rest falls apart.”

Discussions covered interconnections between natural and human environments, focusing on local and regional ecosystems. Participants identified drivers of biodiversity loss, including habitat destruction, pollution, invasive species, overexploitation, and climate change. While scientific terminology was simplified, their understanding of these concepts was evident. It was clear that participants recognised humanity’s dependence on ecosystems, highlighting that protecting biodiversity is essential for survival. Interestingly some discussions landed seamlessly in themes related to Nature Law and the notion that plants and animals deserve rights and protection.

Session 3: Nature walks

Besides many other benefits spending time in nature motivates positive engagement and environmentally protective behaviours. This also served to enhance the general ongoing learning experience, coupling with a fun time, with great benefits to mental health, making sure the session is well balanced, and participants were energised for subsequent activities.

Session 4: What are the five drivers of biodiversity loss?

Participants were divided into five theme groups, each specialising in a key driver of biodiversity loss, defined by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES): habitat loss, climate change, invasive species, overexploitation, and pollution. However, unlike the Family Groups defined at the beginning, each theme group was made up of children and young people of all ages. Each group was tasked with exploring the link between their assigned driver and biodiversity loss. Through creative, participatory methods, the groups explored solutions and developed their understanding of biodiversity loss.

Independent Investigations

To conclude the weekend the Assembly members went to explore biodiversity in their local communities, in between the two Assembly weekends. They were tasked with an independent investigation to identify biodiversity loss looks like in their own community, and what it means to the local communities. The drawing of community maps to tell the story of local biodiversity, and interviews were very much encouraged. This resulted on young people finding importance and value on story-

sharing with older generations, especially in their communities. As the members did not have a perception over a larger span of time, they were unaware that traces of biodiversity had been lost. For example, some plants and birds had disappeared in their area over the years.

Weekend 2: Developing Calls to Action

The second weekend took place at Killarney National Park, County Kerry, and started with a discussion regarding the participants' local investigations, to feed a collective vision and calls to action. On the final day, Assembly members presented their calls to action to Malcolm Noonan TD¹¹, Minister of State for Heritage and Electoral Reform.

Session 1: What does biodiversity loss mean to different people?

The participants engaged in a roleplay exercise simulating a town hall meeting about a proposed housing development¹². Each member assumed the role of a different stakeholder such as: residents, farmers, councillors, developers, members of local ecological groups, children and young people, and families. This exercise highlighted the complexities of balancing biodiversity protection with community needs, once again shedding light on the complexities which must be navigated when dealing with the aforementioned "wicked problems".

Session 2: What are laws and policies, and how can we influence change?

Participants received an overview of Ireland's legal and policy frameworks related to biodiversity, including local, national, European, and global policies and got to examine potential reasons why existing biodiversity policies might have failed to deliver on their objectives, so far.

The discussion introduced the concept of "carrots and sticks"¹³, and the Assembly was quick to advocate for community-focused incentives while enforcing strict penalties for corporations violating biodiversity regulations. At the end, the Lundy Model was used to tailor calls to action for specific audiences, emphasising accountability for those in power.

Key calls to action included enhancing biodiversity education in schools and communities through creative and engaging approaches. Target audiences ranged from families and local communities to global organisations, including local businesses, schools, sports clubs, and government entities. The adult Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss was identified as a priority audience.

¹¹ A Teachta Dála (TD) is a member of Dáil Éireann, the lower house of the Oireachtas (Irish Parliament).

¹² 'Ballydeas' roleplay activity, TRYBE Biodiversity Activity Book, pg. 7. Available at: <https://cyp-biodiversity.ie/resources/> [Accessed 12/12/2024]

¹³ Refers to a motivational strategy that combines rewards (the "carrot") and punishments (the "stick") to influence behavior or outcomes. This approach is often used in management, policymaking, and negotiations to encourage desired actions while discouraging undesirable ones.

Session 3: Introduction to the Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss

The Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss by its Secretary, Art O'Leary, insisted the adults shared their concerns and were discussing similar topics and themes, being on similar ground, and request to hear the young peoples' calls to action at the adult assembly.

Session 4: Creating calls to action

On the very last session, participants were asked to imagine Ireland's future and articulate their aspirations for the country. The Assembly's inputs - over 100 calls to action - were divided into five thematic groups—habitat loss, climate change, invasive species, overexploitation, and pollution. Though there could be noticed a clear overlap on the developed ideas, they later refined into a final vision.

Outcomes and Impact

The final output¹⁴ comprised **6 key messages and 58 calls to action**, categorised into **7 themes**:

- Education & Raising Awareness
- Governance
- Energy & Transport
- Overexploitation
- Habitat & Species Protection
- Restoring & Rewilding
- Waste & Consumption

The calls to action aimed to address pressing biodiversity issues and included proposals for government action. These were later shared with the adult Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss, ensuring the young peoples' perspectives were integrated into ongoing national dialogues. All the calls to action are available in the final report of the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss on its website: <https://cyp-biodiversity.ie/>.

Following the assembly, several follow-up activities took place:

- **November 2022:** Representatives from the children's assembly met with the adult Citizens' Assembly to present its calls to action.

¹⁴ CYPABL (2023), 'Final Report of the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss'. Available at: <https://cyp-biodiversity.ie/> [Accessed 12/12/2024]

- **January 2023:** The Teaching Resources for Youth-informed Biodiversity Education¹⁵ (TRYBE) project launches, picking up on the calls to action from the CYPABL to make more educational resources available for children and young people about biodiversity loss.
- **April 2023:** A final report of the assembly's findings was published on Earth Day, with a video message from Minister Noonan responding to the young peoples' calls to action.
- **October 2023:** A one-year reunion event was held, where the Minister reported back on the actions taken by the government in response to the calls to action. This included the inclusion of youth-driven actions in the newly published National Biodiversity Action Plan.
- **November 2023:** Assembly representatives met with the Oireachtas¹⁶ Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action to discuss the assembly's impact further.
- **June 2024:** The Irish Government published a response document¹⁷ to both the Children and Young People's Assembly and the adult Citizens' Assembly's recommendations on biodiversity loss, providing a line-by-line response to each of the 58 calls to action from the youth assembly and to the 159 recommendations from the adults' assembly.

Lessons learned and best practices for citizen engagement and knowledge transfer

In the context of the Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss, the assembly can be placed between **Consult** and **Involve** on the PREP4BLUE spectrum (Figure 1), where young people were consulted on biodiversity issues and their input informed subsequent national strategy¹⁸. The Assembly's consultative role underscores the challenge of ensuring that young people's contributions lead to real policy change, while respecting the democratic and legal constraints in decision-making processes.

Several key lessons emerged from the Assembly regarding citizen engagement. First, it became evident that involving young people in discussions, particularly those related to environmental issues, requires more time and flexibility than originally anticipated. While the Assembly itself was relatively brief, the preparation, follow-up, and continued advocacy efforts were crucial in ensuring that the Assembly's outcomes were meaningful. This experience highlights the importance of investing

¹⁵ TRYBE project website available here: <https://cyp-biodiversity.ie/resources/> [Accessed 13/12/2024]

¹⁶ Irish Parliament.

¹⁷ Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage (2024), 'Report on Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss & Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss'. Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/en/press-release/67921-government-publishes-response-to-recommendations-of-the-citizens-assembly-on-biodiversity-loss/> [Accessed 13/12/2024]

¹⁸ See Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023-2030, pgs. 3, 4. Available at: https://www.npws.ie/sites/default/files/files/4th_National_Biodiversity_Action_Plan.pdf [Accessed 18/12/2024]

time and resources in the pre- and post-engagement phases, as well as the need for careful planning of timelines.

Additionally, the Assembly underscored the **importance of creating opportunities for intergenerational dialogue by carefully coordinating with adult Citizens' Assembly**. By bringing young people, adults, and policymakers together, the Assembly facilitated a broader conversation about the future of biodiversity and the role of youth in shaping that future. **This intergenerational exchange was valuable not only for the young participants but also for policymakers, who gained insights into the concerns and perspectives of the younger generation.** It was evident that such dialogues are essential for building a shared understanding of the complex issues surrounding environmental sustainability. The assembly's success in fostering this kind of dialogue highlights the need for more opportunities where different generations can work together to develop sustainable solutions to environmental challenges.

Another valuable lesson is **the need to ensure that youth participation is not just symbolic but that it genuinely contributes to policy development.** The assembly's structure allowed for young people to provide meaningful input, but it also revealed the importance of ensuring that these inputs are not only heard but also incorporated into decision-making. In future initiatives, greater efforts should be made to close the loop between citizen engagement and policy outcomes by providing feedback to participants on how their contributions were used in the decision-making process. **This would enhance the transparency of the process and make participants feel that their voices truly matter, which is essential for maintaining trust in participatory processes.**

The Children's and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss serves as an important model for youth engagement in policymaking, particularly in the environmental sector. It demonstrates the potential of young people to drive meaningful change when they are given the opportunity to deliberate on policy decisions. By incorporating young people's voices into decision-making frameworks, governments and organisations can ensure that policies reflect the values and concerns of future generations. The Assembly also highlights the need for greater investment in youth participation, not only as a way to address environmental issues but also as a means of building a more inclusive, democratic society.

4. Workshops – BlueMissionBANOS

Background

BlueMissionBANOS is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) EU Horizon project supporting the implementation of Mission Ocean objectives in the Baltic and North Sea (BANOS) basins. Its objectives are to increase awareness of Mission Ocean, to develop a monitoring framework, facilitate stakeholder collaboration, optimize the deployment of resources, explore synergies with other EU Missions, accelerate the low-carbon and circular economy, and create a transparent and long-term governance structure for Mission Ocean implementation. The project has six Work Packages which are as follows:

- WP1: Project Coordination and Communication
- WP2: Mission Governance in Baltic & North Sea
- WP3: Citizen Engagement (Local workshops: Belgium, Poland, Denmark)
- WP4: Business and Innovation (Mission Arenas)
- WP5: Mission Monitoring in BANOS Area
- WP6: Technical Services Provision ([Wavelinks](#))

Citizen and stakeholder engagement activities are coordinated under WP3 and WP4. This includes the regional stakeholder assemblies known as Mission Arenas, of which there have been three so far (in 2023 and 2024). The Arenas are an opportunity for projects, stakeholders, policy-makers and citizens to come together and discuss common issues of relevance to Mission Ocean, particularly with regard to Mission Ocean Objective III, “Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular”, the focus objective of BlueMissionBANOS and the BANOS Lighthouse. Prior to each Arena, local workshops are held in Denmark, Belgium and Poland by project partners in each of these countries to engage with local citizens with the intention of feeding local knowledge into the regional Arenas. It is these local workshops, and the relationship between the local workshops and the regional stakeholder assemblies, which this case study will focus on.

Mission Arenas and local workshops

The Mission Arenas¹⁹ are designed in the form of stakeholder assemblies, where stakeholders from research, civil society, NGOs, universities, and business come together to discuss common challenges, opportunities, and current initiatives to forward the implementation of Mission Ocean, with a focus on sustainable blue economy. The first Mission Arena was held on 14-16th November 2023 in Gothenburg, Sweden; the second Arena was held on 25-26th April in Riga, Latvia, and the third was held on 26-27th November in Amsterdam, Netherlands.

Figure 4: Schematic representing logic of local and regional workshops (BlueMissionBANOS)

To ensure knowledge transfer, the learnings harnessed in the local workshops, with regard to what *challenges* are faced for citizens to engage in Mission Ocean, and the potential *solutions*, feed into the themes for the Citizen Engagement workshops at the Arenas, with the goal of creating guidelines for future Mission Ocean projects to connect more efficiently with citizens. The themes of the workshops all centre on the green transition in blue economies, such as sustainable aquaculture and seafood production, fisheries, seaweed and mussel production, and offshore energy including wind turbines. In the local workshops, these themes are discussed with local stakeholders and citizens, and questions around how best to involve and engage citizens in Mission Ocean are also discussed, and those learnings fed upstream to the Arenas (Figure 4).

Local workshops in Denmark and Belgium

For this case study, we will focus on the local workshops held in Belgium and Denmark in 2023 and 2024. In Belgium, the focus area for the local workshop was the Belgian North Sea Coast, and in Denmark, the focus was on the Danish Straits. At these workshops, a mix of citizens and stakeholders attended including also students, NGOs, public engagement experts, blue economy experts and representatives of academia and research.

¹⁹ More information on the Mission Arenas is available here: <https://bluemissionbanos.eu/events/>

In Denmark, in 2023 and 2024, the Danish climate policy festival Klimafolkemødet (EN: The Climate Festival) was chosen as the venue for the local workshops. Klimafolkemødet is an annual climate-themed festival designed to inspire action on climate change. It runs as a forum including workshops, discussions, talks, cultural events and concerts to promote climate change solutions and to inspire new solutions and change.

Figure 5: Klimafolkemødet banner

It is free to attend, both as an organiser and as an attendee. In 2024, 40,000 people attended which is the largest festival so far since it began in 2017, offering 400 debates, talks, workshops and cultural events and over 100 stalls and booths. It is well attended both by ordinary

citizens and by politicians and professionals, such as researchers – as such, it provided an ideal venue for the local BlueMissionBANOS Danish workshops.

In 2023, the BlueMissionBANOS Danish local workshop was held on November 1st (a Friday) at the Klimafolkemødet; in 2024, it was held on August 31st (a Saturday). At the first workshop, blue energy infrastructure (mainly offshore wind) was discussed, while at the second workshop the focus was on sustainable aquaculture and seafood production (mainly seaweed and blue mussel production) – both times, the challenges of involving citizens in policy and research around these themes was also discussed. The Klimafolkemødet venue was chosen because of the high volume of interested citizens in the area, and the

Figure 6: Local workshop in Denmark (BlueMissionBANOS)

fact that it is free to attend, which removes potential financial barriers to engagement. In terms of demographics, both workshops had slightly higher male attendance, with the age profiles leaning towards late 20s to late 50s, with a handful of attendees in their 60s and 70s. In the 2023 local workshop, notably more professionals attended as opposed to the 2024 workshop, due to the 2023 workshop being held on a Friday during working hours. In the 2024 workshop, more citizens attended as opposed to professionals, possibly due to it being held on a Saturday.

Another factor possibly influencing the interest of citizens to attend the workshop in 2024 was the topic being sustainable seafood as opposed to offshore renewable energy, since food is a more relatable and tangible topic for ordinary citizens. Additionally, there has been increasing interest recently in Denmark for sustainable seafood production with the increasing popularity of marine allotment gardens²⁰, allowing individuals to grow their own seafood such as mussels and seaweed. As such, some of the citizens who attended were already interested in the discussion topic. In both cases, participants mostly had some background knowledge of the topics, or a degree of professional knowledge. In both Danish workshops, breakout groups and brainstorming methods were used: each table seated 4-5 people and the participants used large sheets of paper and sticky notes to make notes of their discussions which was led by the facilitator using questions on needs and solutions. Both Danish workshops lasted for 45 minutes each.

Figure 7: Local workshop in Belgium (BlueMissionBANOS)

For the Belgium workshops, the venue was the Flanders Marine Institute (Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee, VLIZ). This choice resulted in higher attendance of professionals, researchers and academics as opposed to ordinary citizens – however, this created a space for the citizens who were participating to learn from many different professional experiences, and also for professionals to learn from local citizens' experiences. The workshops have also been held on weekdays, again allowing easier access for professionals. In terms of facilitation and methods, breakout groups were used with each having access to sticky notes and large sheets of paper were used to collate participants' perspectives, and were displayed on a glass wall (Figure 9). The workshops lasted for 2 hours.

The workshops in Denmark were advertised in many different ways, in an attempt to secure as many diverse participants as possible. Professional groups and NGO representatives were

Saturday 11:00 | Orange

Dialogue about the green foods of the sea

Come and join a round table discussion (world cafe style) between different stakeholder groups and citizens, about the best solutions for involving citizens in terms of aquaculture and sustainable production of climate-friendly food from the sea.

Figure 8: Advertisement of BlueMissionBANOS workshop on Klimafolkemødet website

²⁰ Orange, R. 'Grow your own mussels: the new phenomenon of sea allotments', The Guardian online, 25 June 2022. Available online: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2022/jun/25/denmark-sea-allotments-rise> [Accessed 04/11/2024]

contacted via direct invites, and the workshop was also advertised through LinkedIn to attract professional audiences. The workshop was also included in the festival programme²¹ on the website (<https://klimafolkemoedet.dk/>) and at a booth organised by the University of Southern Denmark, the BlueMissionBANOS project partner who also organised the workshop. Finally, as for all Klimafolkemødet workshops, the workshop was also advertised through a loudspeaker system at the

Figure 9: Brainstorming post-it notes from local workshop in Belgium (BlueMissionBANOS)

festival and by festival attendees spreading the message into the streets near the venue. As for the local workshops in Belgium, with the intention being to attract more professional attendees, the advertising focused more on existing networks known to VLIZ: this included sending the details of the workshop to a mailing list and advertising it around local communities living nearby the institute.

In terms of feedback received from participants, no formal feedback forms were used in

either the Belgium or Denmark workshops – however, informal oral feedback was given at the end of both workshops, and this was generally positive, with people praising the organisation of the workshops, the methods used and the interesting discussion matter. Some participants attending the workshops also indicated their interest in future participation in upcoming workshops.

Lessons learned and best practices for citizen engagement and knowledge transfer

Workshops can be placed in between Consult and Involve on the PREP4BLUE spectrum (Figure 1) since they can be a form of two-way knowledge transfer: participants can learn more about programmes and initiatives throughout the workshop, but they also have a chance to be directly involved in the outcomes and focal points of such initiatives through participating in the workshop. In the case of the BlueMissionBANOS local workshops, they are situated in between Consult and Involve since they offer a space for citizens to be directly involved in Mission Ocean, in a one off manner, while not necessarily becoming a partner in the development of new programmes.

Regarding lessons learned for citizen engagement, a key message from the local workshops in Denmark is to **consider how the date and time of your workshop impacts on the availability of citizens**. In 2023, the local workshop in Denmark was hosted on a

²¹ Klimafolkemødet 2024 festival programme. Available at: <https://klimafolkemoedet.dk/program2024/> [Accessed 04/11/2024]

Friday during working hours, meaning that more professionals and policy makers attended (both types of professions regularly attend Klimafolkemødet). However, in 2024, it was hosted on a Saturday, and as a result, a higher proportion of ordinary citizens attended. This small difference in scheduling had a big impact on the workshops on the day in terms of demographics, key themes discussed, and outcomes.

Similarly, another point to consider is to **make sure you have enough time set aside during your workshop** to discuss issues in sufficient depth. In the case of the local workshops in Denmark, the workshops had to fit within the schedule set by the festival organisers, which was 45 minutes. While the venue (Klimafolkemødet) ensured a more diverse set of participants, the restricted timing impacted on the depth of the discussion. Conversely, in the case of the local workshops in Belgium, the organisers had 2 hours at their disposal which allowed for more deep and thoughtful discussions.

With regard to the setting of the workshop, from the local workshop in Denmark, another learning related to the chosen setting being a climate policy festival. While undoubtedly this resulted in a diverse range of citizens engaged, **it is important to keep in mind that the people who attend such events are normally already engaged with and thinking about climate change**. However, this also benefited the discussion as it resulted in a **more informed discussion**.

Relating to the above points, it is also important to **try to align your workshop topic to topics already in the public discourse**, to ensure a more informed discussion and also to make the topic interesting and relevant to citizens, to encourage a higher and more diverse attendance. **The topic should also be accessible** to citizens (this does not mean "dumbing down" the issue, but rather explaining how the topic is relevant and impactful for the citizens in an understandable and engaging manner).

Gathering formal feedback in the form of feedback forms, either on paper or virtually such as through Google Forms, Microsoft Forms, or SurveyMonkey, is another learning from both workshops. This not only helps to **improve the development and planning of future workshops**, but also allows the organisers a chance to formally gather demographic information (such as age, gender, race, and institution/background, if applicable). However this should be done anonymously, and demographical questions should be optional, so that respondents are encouraged to answer as truthfully as possible.

An additional benefit of hosting in-person workshops with citizens is that citizens tend to appreciate genuine engagement at local levels with international programmes – they recognise that it is more difficult, but it is more rewarding for both the researcher and for the citizen, when done properly. Citizens recognise the importance of linking up research, policy, and society and generally are willing to contribute, **as long as the value of their contributions is clearly communicated**. This links to the benefit of hosting workshops in forums where citizens are already congregating, such as science festivals, to make the interlinkages between science and policy clearer, and to **make the effort to come to citizens, rather than asking the citizens to come to you**. In the context of European projects particularly, the role of citizens is key in bringing the EU down to the local level and communicating the importance of such initiatives.

5. Attitude surveys – EastSide Greenways

Background

EastSide Greenways is a Belfast-based local regeneration charity which is situated under the umbrella charity EastSide Partnership²². Originally established as the Connswater Community Greenway Trust, in 2007, an application for development of a new greenway along the Conns Water River in east Belfast won £23 million of funding from the National Lottery and an additional £17 million from other sources, including the Department for Infrastructure and the Department for Communities.

With work completed in 2017, EastSide Greenways was then established to co-manage and maintain the greenway²³, with a focus on local community engagement and fostering community stewardship of the greenway (meanwhile, Belfast City Council manages and maintains the greenway infrastructure, and owns the land on which the greenway is built). Its sister charities within the partnership also examine regeneration through different lenses, including art, property, tourism, and education. EastSide Greenways currently has 12 regular volunteers who volunteer on a monthly basis, and 9 occasional staff, who work on an ad-hoc basis, and 4 full-time staff. It's award-winning community engagement model, including winning the Great Place Award at the 2020 Urbanism Awards in London²⁴ ²⁵, is the subject of this case study, with a particular focus on surveys as a method of citizen engagement.

The east side of Belfast has been identified as a socially deprived area in assessments made by multiple agencies, including the Education Authority²⁶ and the Northern Ireland Assembly²⁷ - with problems such as low attendance levels of third level education, relatively high teen birth rates, and poorer health outcomes persisting. In this context, it was identified as important to keep the local community engaged with the greenway on an ongoing basis after the completion of works in 2017, to maintain its positive legacy impact and to manage the potential for anti-social behaviour at an early stage.

²² EastSide Partnership also comprises EastSide Learning, EastSide Arts, EastSide Tourism, EastSide Property, as well as EastSide Greenways.

²³ Fetherston, S. (2024), 'Have you heard of the urban greenway in East Belfast?', RTE Online, Available at: <https://www.rte.ie/lifestyle/travel/2024/0605/1453104-have-you-heard-of-the-urban-greenway-in-east-belfast/> [Accessed 13/11/2024]

²⁴ Academy of Urbanism (2020), 'Connswater Community Greenway, Belfast. Assessment for The Great Place Award 2020', Available at: <https://www.theaou.org/resources/connswater-community-greenway> [Accessed 13/11/2024]

²⁵ EastSide Partnership (2019), 'Connswater Community Greenway Wins Great Place Award', Available at: <https://www.eastsidepartnership.com/news/ccg-wins-great-place-award> [Accessed 13/11/2024]

²⁶ Education Authority (2023), 'Local Assessment of Need: North and East Belfast' Report, pg. 11.

²⁷ Northern Ireland Assembly (2017), 'Constituency Profile – Belfast East' Report.

Surveys as used by Eastside Greenways

The ethos behind EastSide Greenways' community engagement model, where surveys as a method of citizen engagement play a key role, reflects principles of stewardship and participation by fostering a shared sense of ownership over the greenway among local residents and stakeholders. This is with the goal of ensuring the Connswater Community Greenway remains a sustainable amenity which local

people will enjoy using for many years to come.

Figure 10: Example of an outdoor survey data collection method (EastSide Greenways)

In EastSide Greenways' work, surveys are a key component and are used as a method of both data collection and citizen engagement in a variety of ways. Both online and in-person surveys are used, depending on the purpose and circumstances. For example, after the Covid-19 lockdown ended, an in-person survey²⁸ was carried out outdoors on the path of the greenway to examine users' experiences of the greenway during the pandemic. Noticing a distinct increase in foot traffic on the greenway, due to the indoor meeting restrictions, EastSide Greenways decided to survey users to see how their perceptions of the greenway had changed or been impacted by Covid-19. The survey discovered that the greenway had essentially become an outdoor community centre, during a time when

people were not allowed to use their local indoor community centre. During the lockdown, EastSide Greenways also facilitated many outdoor community events which normally would have been held indoors, increasing use of the greenway.

This survey was held outdoors and included a strong citizen engagement aspect. EastSide Greenways conducted the survey, with the help of volunteers, in six locations along the greenway for approximately an hour and a half 1-2 times per week for the duration of the survey. Pop-up gazebo structures were used to shelter participants from the rain, and to provide a space for citizen engagement, which included art-based methods (e.g. colouring in sheets for children), and resources which survey

²⁸ EastSide Partnership (2020), 'Greenway on the Go' survey results, Available at: <https://www.eastsidegreenways.com/user-stories/> [accessed 13/11/2024]

respondents could take away (e.g. a treasure trail of the greenway). The results of this survey are displayed on the website in a graphic²⁹ (Figure 11).

Figure 11: 'Greenway on the Go' graphic with key quotes from survey respondents (EastSide Greenway)

EastSide Greenways also does online surveys, using the SurveyMonkey platform to administer these surveys. The organization has also developed a set of best practices around online surveys, including limiting questions to 10 or fewer, to avoid burdening respondents with too much information. In online surveys, demographic questions are also kept to a minimum and are made as easy as possible for respondents to answer (e.g. providing an age scale range instead of asking respondents to input their actual age – it takes fractionally less time for a respondent to click, for example, '18-25' rather than to input their actual age; additionally, respondents may not want to give too much information which could be used to identify them). EastSide Greenways also has a robust strategy for dissemination of its online surveys, including its social media pages such as Facebook (where the charity has over 10,000 followers) and local community Facebook groups, and also through its extensive network of partners and collaborators including community organisations, stakeholders, and residents' groups. EastSide Greenways is also involved in impact evaluation work coordinated by Queens University Belfast, which is examining the long-term impact on the community before and after the construction of the greenway, which has engaged 1,200 local residents.

²⁹ Ibid.

Surveys: Lessons learned and best practices for citizen engagement and knowledge transfer

Within the context of the use of surveys as a citizen engagement method by EastSide Greenways, surveys in this instance can fall between **Consult** and **Involve** on the PREP4BLUE framework (Figure 1). However, depending on what is done with the data, and what other methods of engagement are used alongside surveys, this method can move further along the scale to **Collaborate**. For example, if surveys are co-designed with respondents or focus-grouped ahead of time.

Within EastSide Greenways, knowledge transfer in surveys as a method of citizen engagement is well embedded in the organisation's community engagement model.

Surveys are essentially used for three distinct, but overlapping, purposes:

1. As an organization, EastSide Greenways is very well embedded in the local community, nurturing strong relationships both with local residents' groups, volunteers, stakeholders, partners, researchers and universities, and local businesses. Surveys can be a method for EastSide Greenways to formalize what the organisation already knows to be true based on informal conversations and connections with local residents and stakeholders.
2. EastSide Greenways is also embedded in local policymaking and local politics, and survey data can be a way to inform strategic conversations around use of the greenway.
3. Survey data also directly informs the work of EastSide Greenways – for example, if the charity runs a survey and discovers users wish to improve a particular aspect or area along the greenway, this is something EastSide Greenways can work on in collaboration with partners.

Regarding knowledge transfer, a best practice identified by EastSide Greenways is to **ensure the survey is relevant to the respondents you wish to target**, in this case citizens. If citizens are asked to respond to a survey on a topic they don't know anything about, or which is not relevant to them, they are more likely to be disengaged or to provide the wrong type of information, through no fault of their own. This is why co-creating surveys with a representative sample of respondents can be a good idea. It is important to recognise that no 'one size fits all' approach is always suitable for surveys – **however, where surveys are being used over a longer period of time, standardisation may be appropriate** (such as for tracking and evidencing impacts). This long-term impact measurement is important for demonstrating impact which downstream can lead to more strategic partnerships and funding for future initiatives.

Another best practice to keep in mind for citizen engagement when using surveys is to be **mindful of survey design**. EastSide Greenways limits their surveys to 10 questions or fewer and does not ask too many personal identifying questions (such as age or location). For example, by asking residents to input their area postcode into a survey, as opposed to their address, EastSide Greenways can quickly identify whether a respondent actually lives in the area or not without asking them to disclose too much information. Again, when designing attitude surveys for citizens, sometimes a flexible approach is best: EastSide Greenways employs both online and in-person surveys, with

different purposes in mind, depending on the type of data they wish to collect, and how that data will be used.

As a method of citizen engagement (and participation), surveys can be used to the benefit of all parties when **EastSide Greenway volunteers are tasked with administering the data collection in-person**. For example, regarding the 'Greenway on the Go' survey, **volunteers were asked to assist at the gazebos where the survey was being conducted and administer the surveys themselves**. Survey respondents would have a conversation with volunteers in which they would be informed about the survey, its aims and methods, and would be asked about their experiences using the greenway during the Covid-19 lockdown. This, combined with the art-based methods of engagement at the gazebos, made the survey more engaging for respondents. Additionally, the survey presented the opportunity for **citizen participation through the use of volunteer administrators**, who were tasked with asking questions, writing the answers, and managing the safe and secure handling of the paper survey forms and management at the gazebos. **This not only benefits the charity from volunteer support, but also has benefits for volunteers themselves, such as building new skills and experience.**

However, it is important to highlight that **surveys as a method of citizen engagement work best when combined with other methods**, and when **embedded into long-term structures** such as non-governmental organizations, so that the data and knowledge gathered can be translated into meaningful action, and so that this can be demonstrated to citizens. The local context is also important: stewardship over the local area is important for the residents near the Connswater Community Greenway, so that the potential for anti-social behaviour in a socially deprived area can be reduced from the outset. Surveys are just one method, in a toolbox of many others, which EastSide Greenway employs to achieve this and are at their most impactful when employed in conjunction with other engagement methods.

6. Citizen science surveys – COSEA

Background

SPOTTERON³⁰ is a citizen science app platform, specialising in the development and provision of mobile apps, interactive web-applications, digital science media, and websites, which can be used by multi-national research projects, regional/national projects, or local community groups. Their unique model of app development makes their products very user-friendly, feature-rich, and compatible at all levels of research and investigation, with strong community-building and science communication aspects. SPOTTERON's mobile apps are designed to be modular, meaning that the inherit structure of the app can be replicated and tweaked, and new features can be added which can be replicated across all previous apps.

The COSEA³¹ app is one of SPOTTERON's latest addition and is as a result of collaboration with the EU research projects TRANSEATION and EFFECTIVE. With both projects covering different themes (TRANSEATION focuses on blue economy and restoration, while EFFECTIVE focuses on Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)), and COSEA being co-funded by both projects, this allows the app to have a more holistic approach towards citizen science data collection at coastlines and digital-social community interaction. This case study will focus on the COSEA app, and on SPOTTERON's app development ethos, with implications for digital app-based methods of citizen science survey data collection.

Mobile app-based citizen science data collection

The COSEA app is free to download on Google Play or the Apple App Store, making it an accessible way to engage in citizen science. In addition, the app is available as a web-application accessible via a browser, which also allows data contributions and user activity. It is also designed to be flexible and interactive for each user, allowing users an individual participation experience on the app. When users first register on the app, they are invited to fill in optional personal details (including their occupation and how their work relates to marine and coastal environments), and their level of familiarity with the coast. Some of the occupations (or 'roles') provided as options include local residents, tourists, fishers, divers, and science communicators. However, all user profile information is optional, and users are not asked to provide their full names if they do not want to – there is an option to provide a pseudonym.

Users are then invited to submit 'spots', which are essentially datapoints with attached photos of a species, object, or feature they have observed on their coastline. When uploading a new 'spot', they are prompted to select one of the following six

³⁰ Visit SPOTTERON's website for more info: <https://www.spotteron.net/> [Accessed 12/12/2024]

³¹ COSEA application available here: <https://www.spotteron.com/cosea/> [Accessed 12/12/2024]

categories: Habitat, Species, Pollution, Activities, Economy, or Infrastructure (Figure 12). The app then responds to what choice the user has made, prompting them to

Figure 12: 'Add Spot' screen on COSEA app (screenshot by Catriona Reid)

input more data about their observation. For example, if a user selects 'Habitat', they can then select which habitat it is they have observed from a drop-down menu, and can also read background information about different habitat types to inform their choice. If they have chosen 'Habitat', they are also prompted to draw the outline of the habitat on the app (Figure 13).

The same principle applies to the six other options: in each case, a user is asked to provide more detail relevant to the observation. For example, if a user selects 'Infrastructure', they are prompted to assess more details about the type and the condition and type of coastal infrastructure. If a user selects 'Species', they are asked to select a group or species from a drop-down list – and so on.

In all cases, users are then asked to provide a photograph, which they can either select from their phone's photo gallery, or they can take a photo in the app and upload it directly. Users can also provide any additional notes they wish, and are asked to disclose how the observation makes them 'feel' ranging on a scale from happy to sad (Figure 13).

Once a user's first 'spot' has been uploaded, they are notified with an automated message from the app congratulating them on their first 'spot'. This is part of an in-app awards and badge system, where users are awarded for their contributions to citizen science.

The COSEA app also provides the opportunity for users to interact with each other, forming a sense of community around citizen science – users can follow each other, 'like' and comment on each other's spots and profiles, and moderators can also 'validate' spots to have a contribution in the app be verified by an expert. For direct community interactions it is possible to tag another user ('@username'), in which case the tagged user receives a push notification on her or his mobile device which leads directly to the tagged comment. Secondly, project partners in COSEA and other SPOTTERON apps are able to send custom media-rich messages to all participants about project news, discoveries, or educational content, which also arrives at the users' devices with a push notification. This allows project partners in COSEA to inform the community, disseminate news and facts, and directly support ongoing user motivation by fostering in-app activity and knowledge transfer.

Furthermore, the SPOTTERON platform features like interactive map overlays with data visualizations, statistics, user leader-boards, data filters, project activities and events,

and other integrated elements provide a multilevel digital environment for citizen science participation, data exploration, and community building.

It is also planned that the COSEA app will become a citizen science resource internationally, allowing researchers, NGOs or other stakeholders to directly access the regional or global data and get statistics and data summaries from their own region or area – ensuring the knowledge transfer aspect of this app, as the data will not exist statically in the app, but can be used for future research. Additionally, it is planned that when user-submitted data is used by researchers in the future, users which uploaded those data points will be notified to tell them that their 'spot' is being used in research or impact generation as part of a project data-set and project partner dashboard.

Figure 13: 'Add Spot' screen where users are prompted to add a picture of their observation and describe how it makes them feel (left), and draw an outline on an observed habitat (right) (screenshot by Catriona Reid)

Lessons learned and best practices for citizen engagement and knowledge transfer

With regard to citizen engagement, when using digital apps, **user security and privacy** is a key issue to keep in mind: removing the requirement, for example, for users to submit their full names is one way to ensure that users can remain as anonymous as possible. Additionally, having the proper digital safeguards in place to protect user data is essential, particularly when handling sensitive data such as birthdates and email addresses. Most important for applied online privacy in general is data minimisation and avoidance of user surveillance. By consciously not implementing third party tracking services like analytics or social media platform elements, users can

be protected from constant surveillance of their online activity. In contrast to many other citizen science and participatory platforms and apps, on SPOTTERON this core principle of not enforcing constant online surveillance on citizen science participants is implemented. This applied privacy ethic and its practice is even more essential in public-funded digital toolkits and apps, not only but especially in citizen science projects taking place in the European Union.

Building in a feedback system to a digital application is another key way to increase user engagement – the social element of the SPOTTERON apps is one which has allowed citizen science communities to pop up all around the world, as users interact with each other in the app, and enjoy the element of light competition that exists with the badge reward system. Allowing users to see that they are not alone in their data collection, and letting them build up their own relationships and networks through the app, keeps users engaged long-term – not only in the app, but also in citizen science.

Expert validation is another key element, both for **citizen engagement and knowledge transfer** in citizen science – users should not be expected to be experts, and it is not only important for research data validation purposes to validate user-submitted spots, but also so that users can see whether their inputs have been received, seen, acknowledged, and verified. This is also important for educational purposes: users can learn from their mistakes, and can get feedback from experts, through a built-in system of expert validation. The plans for ensuring the legacy of the COSEA app, with the option for **researchers to access the data in the future and feedback directly to users**, once the app is fully operational, also is a promising aspect both for citizen engagement and knowledge transfer.

In general regarding citizen science, as a guiding principle, having a flexible, user-friendly approach is important – in other words, **a data collection system which blends seamlessly into citizens' everyday lives**. With the majority of people having a phone in their pocket, across all generations, mobile app-based methods can be a highly effective way to gather data, and engage citizens in the process, while not intruding too much on citizens' lives, being considerate of differing abilities, time constraints, and levels of interest.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Citizen engagement is a cornerstone of effective governance³², fostering trust, inclusivity, and transparency, and its importance to the implementation of Mission Ocean is recognised and highlighted in the Mission Implementation Plan. With a grounding in sociological and political science theories of participatory and deliberative democracy, this report has examined three different methods of citizen engagement, and highlighted best practices in four case studies:

5. **Citizen Assemblies** (Ireland's Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss)
6. **Workshops** (BlueMissionBANOS's local workshops and regional Mission Arenas)
7. **Attitudinal surveys** (EastSide Partnership)
8. **Citizen science surveys** (SPOTTERON COSEA mobile app)

Knowledge transfer is a key element of citizen engagement, and when done correctly can contribute to a feedback loop paving the way for future citizen engagement, on the basis of citizens understanding how their contributions are valued and feeling welcome to contribute again. Processes of knowledge transfer and knowledge exchange can also be incredibly beneficial for ensuring that solutions to climate change are inclusive and beneficial to all members of society.

The impact had by the conceptual design and structure of citizen engagement methods is also an important factor to consider. For example, whether or not a Citizens' Assembly is mandated to follow up on the recommendations made by the participating citizens, to incorporate their conclusions into policy or legal instruments, will have an effect on the actual and perceived impact of the process³³. In democracies, the *perception* of democracy is almost as important as the *actual* democratic process³⁴. Key is to build-in a follow-up or implementation mechanism, which the mandating authority (be it a local or national government) is obliged to follow.

Limitations of citizen engagement

Despite best efforts, citizen engagement initiatives and efforts can have limitations and risks, leading to challenges in implementation. These can include but are not limited to: costs of participation for citizens, and costs of implementation; stakeholder fatigue and 'tokenistic' participation; low or lack of incentives for participation; weak links to policy implementation; and language or information barriers (i.e. low public understanding of scientific practice, or reliance on overly technical language).

³² OECD (2023), 'Open Government for Stronger Democracies: A Global Assessment', OECD Publishing, Paris. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1787/5478db5b-en>.

³³ Willis, R., Curato, N., & Smith, G. (2022), 'Deliberative democracy and the climate crisis', *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 13(2), e759. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.759>

³⁴ Pow, J., van Dijk, L., & Marien, S. (2020). 'It's Not Just the Taking Part that Counts: 'Like Me' Perceptions Connect the Wider Public to Minipublics', *Journal of Deliberative Democracy*, 16(2), 43-55. <https://doi.org/10.16997/jdd.368>

Costs of participation can include financial costs as well as time and resources (e.g. the time it takes for a citizen to travel to a workshop, or the financial costs of arranging for childcare or transport). When not properly addressed, these costs can turn into barriers to participation, with the undesirable effect of potentially lowering levels of participation among communities who feel these barriers most acutely. Implementation costs, meanwhile, can limit citizen engagement by limiting its scope, impact, and outreach – in some cases, the fewer financial and staffing resources allocated to citizen engagement, the less impactful these efforts will be³⁵.

An additional challenge associated with citizen engagement is the need for a feedback or follow-up mechanism with citizens – informing them of resulting policy changes, new legislation, or outputs from their engagement. This follow-up mechanism is essential to any citizen engagement process in the interests of democratising science and opening up policy-making processes, enhancing their legitimacy. However, feedback mechanisms can be difficult to build into a project at the proposal stage. This means a commitment on the part of the individual researchers to follow up with participants after a project or initiative has ended³⁶.

Stakeholder fatigue is a very real concern when implementing a citizen engagement initiative – this is when a group of stakeholders or citizens are repeatedly engaged over the course of different initiatives, which can lead to lower levels of interest over time. This is especially likely to happen if the stakeholders perceive that their input has had no impact or effect – regardless of whether or not this is actually the case. A related issue is that of lacking or low incentives for participation, which can exacerbate stakeholder fatigue over time. By not providing sufficient incentives for participation (financial compensation, opportunities for deeper engagement, or opportunities for broader influence), citizens may not feel that their efforts have been appreciated and this may decrease their willingness to participate in future efforts³⁷.

Weak links to policy implementation are another critical point where citizen engagement efforts may fail. This is a risk as it can result in a legitimacy deficit, where the recommendations, results, or outputs of a citizen engagement effort are seen as having little legitimacy because they are not impactful, making the efforts appear trivial. This can also have the effect of reducing the overall perception of citizen engagement efforts more broadly, as the failures of implementation of one engagement may be seen as failures of citizen engagement broadly speaking³⁸.

Language barriers are another way that citizen engagement efforts may fail – where inadequate translation services are provided, or when technical language is not simplified to a level where a non-expert may understand it. Citizens might feel overwhelmed with information or patronised if technical language barriers are not

³⁵ Shannon, L. et. al., (2019). 'Furthering Citizen Engagement in Local Authority Budgetary Processes Through Participatory Budgeting In Ireland', Local Government Research Series No. 15, Institute of Public Administration.

³⁶ Langkjær, F. and Smith, G., (2023). 'Designing the Follow-Up to Climate Assemblies'. Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies Briefing No. 8.

³⁷ Fung, A., (2015). 'Putting the Public Back into Governance: The Challenges of Citizen Participation and Its Future', *Public Administration Review*, 75:4, 513-522. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12361>

³⁸ *ibid.*

overcome in an appropriate manner (i.e. making technical terms understandable to the average audience, without 'dumbing down')³⁹.

Recommendations

To conclude, a range of citizen engagement and knowledge transfer processes will be needed to ensure a range of knowledges and perspectives contribute to the implementation of Mission Ocean. Some of the best practices identified by the findings of this research include:

General guiding principles and best practices

- Intergenerational dialogue is a key part of citizen engagement, particularly when involving children, to foster greater understanding of common issues, and compassion between generations.
- Aligning your local or small-scale initiative with a national, international, or larger-scale initiative (e.g. the CYPABL aligning with the national Irish Citizens' Assembly on Biodiversity Loss; the local BlueMissionBANOS workshops feeding into the international Mission Arenas), when possible, can greatly benefit your initiative and increase its impact and reach.
- Aligning your discussion points with citizens with issues already in the public discourse (e.g. in the local Danish BlueMissionBANOS workshops, the citizens discussed aquaculture, which is a talking point in national media), can help both in making the issue more relatable to citizens, and in informing the discussions you have with them.
- When possible, particularly when testing or piloting a model of engagement never before done in a particular context, try to align your conceptual logic model with existing conceptual frameworks of citizen participation (find references in the bibliography of this document).
- Incorporate a flexible approach into your initiative design from the beginning, allowing time for adjustments and delays.

Communicating with the public

- When communicating with the public about climate change issues, it is important to be honest and upfront about the issues, and not shy away from having potentially difficult conversations – however, it is important to recognise the duty of care that must be had when engaging with the public, and especially so when engaging with young people.
- Follow-up is very important: the more that you engage with citizens, the more that they may expect to receive in return for their engagement, in terms of impacts and results. It is important to be honest, if you expect that impacts will

³⁹ Bastos, A., Simeone Henriques, M., & Wilkinson, C. (2019), 'The potential opportunities and limitations of Public Engagement in Science and Technology', *Interin*, 24:2, 173-186. Available at: <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=504459802012> [Accessed 08/08/2025]

be limited or small-scale. However, if your engagement with citizens is very impactful, then it is important to communicate this with the individuals who engaged (e.g. through a GDPR-compliant email newsletter). On a systemic scale, follow-up from institutions or governments is also very important (e.g. the Irish government's response to the CYPABL and the CABL).

- Following up with citizens is not only important to demonstrate, on an individual level, the impact of their participation, but on a societal level, follow-up is also important for the sake of transparency, honesty, and instilling trust in democratic and knowledge production processes.
- If you are planning for longer-term engagement, for example repetitive surveys or longitudinal studies, the format should be as accessible as possible for citizens, and should blend as seamlessly as possible into their everyday lives.
- If using citizen science as a method of citizen engagement, expert validation of user-submitted data is very important, both for validating the dataset, communicating the value of citizens' contributions, and in educating citizens.
- Reflective evaluation – when a citizen engagement initiative or process has completed, having a reflective discussion within your own staff team can be very beneficial, both for informing future practice and discussing mistakes, challenges, and opportunities faced along the way.
- Impact evaluation – when possible, organizing a follow-up impact assessment process (e.g. a focus group) with the participating citizens can be a good way to harness learnings, discuss challenges and opportunities, and learn from mistakes with citizens. This can be facilitated by an external evaluator, or, if appropriate, can be done by the project team who conducted the initial engagement.

Facilitation and practical considerations

- Ask participants in a workshop to agree on a 'charter' (e.g., 'I won't interrupt you while you're speaking, so don't interrupt me when I'm speaking')
- Pre-preparing citizens for citizen engagement may sometimes be necessary, if involving them in a long-term initiative (e.g. host a Zoom webinar beforehand to introduce them to the decision-making process or initiative)
- The involvement of specialist facilitators may sometimes be necessary for ensuring optimal citizen engagement outcomes (e.g. the involvement of Terres des Hommes in the CYPABL)
- Exercises, such as roleplay exercises or gamification, can be a useful tool to encourage participants to think outside of their own comfort zone and put themselves in the shoes of another stakeholder (e.g. the Ballydeas roleplay activity in the CYPABL)
- Consider how the chosen date and time of your workshop or event may influence levels and type of attendance (e.g. hosting an event on a weekend)

may attract more ordinary citizens, vs hosting an event on a weekday attracting more professionals)

- Gather formal feedback at the end of every citizen engagement, if possible, to inform and improve future events
- If appropriate, involve citizens in the implementation and planning of an initiative (e.g. the Young Advisory Team in the CYPABL, or the involvement of volunteers in collecting survey data in the EastSide Partnership outdoor surveys)

Table 1: Synthesis of findings from analysis of case studies

	Workshops	Citizen Assemblies	Citizen science apps	Surveys
General recommendations	Align with a larger initiative if possible, at national or local level	Embed intergenerational dialogue in the deliberation phase	Make data collection as easy and accessible as possible for citizens	Beta test your survey with respondents if possible
Communicating with the public	Be honest and upfront about climate change, avoiding sugarcoating or over-simplification	Embed an institutional follow-up process to ensure maximum impact of citizens' recommendations	Expert validation of citizen-submitted data is essential	Phrase questions carefully so as not to sway respondents' answers
Practical considerations	Give thought to the time and date of your workshop, and accessibility requirements of your participants	Pre-prepare citizens for engagement, through a webinar or workshop	Ensure data sensitivity and adherence to GDPR requirements	Give consideration to whether your survey will be filled out online or in person – this will have implications for the length and type of questions asked.

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9. Appendix A

This appendix includes a list of the key questions which were asked of the case studies during the semi-structured interviews.

Overview/background:

- What type of engagement did you do?
- What problem were you looking for input on?
- What demographic of citizens did you engage and how many?
- How long did your engagement run for?
- Which project/institution/initiative coordinated this engagement?

Citizen engagement questions:

- What level of engagement/participation did the citizens involved have? (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower)
- Why did you choose this level of engagement/participation?
- Do you think it was successful?
- What factors contributed to its success/failure?

Impact/evaluation

- Did you solicit feedback from citizens? Was this feedback positive/negative, and why? Did the citizens indicate that they felt they had reached the level of engagement you set out to achieve? (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower)
- What do you think you could have done better?
- What worked well, and what didn't work well?
- What lessons/advice would you have for people doing similar such engagements in the future?
- What do you see as the role of citizens in Mission Ocean – how do you see the role of facilitators of citizen engagement as being in this context?

Citizen Assemblies

(If your project organizes Citizen Assemblies, the following questions focus on inclusivity, deliberation processes, and follow-up actions.)

Before:

- How did you address common barriers to inclusivity? (Venue, remuneration, etc)
- What was the question you wanted the citizens to answer?
- How did you involve stakeholders/citizens/experts in the design of your assembly?
- What language was the assembly in?
- How did you select your citizen participants? What criteria?

During:

- How long did you give the citizens for deliberation?
- How did you ensure that the deliberation was fair?
- What did you consider to be
- Did you have observers in the room present during the deliberations/plenary? (jurors, researchers, etc)

After:

- How did you support the citizens to make their recommendations? (eg legal translation, minority support, etc)
- What happened to their recommendations?
- Did you follow up with the citizens involved?

Online Events:

- Did you offer guidance for citizens on how to use online tools? Jamboard, Zoom, Teams, etc
- Did you offer guidance to the facilitators on how to use online tools? Did the facilitators feel confident in doing so?
- How did you manage technical issues, such as call/video interruptions, etc?
- In your opinion how high was the quality of the deliberation in the online setting? Do you think that the online setting was a benefit or a hindrance to the quality of the deliberation?

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